

**ALIGNMENT OF COGNITIVE PROCESS AND KNOWLEDGE DIMENSIONS WITH
LEARNING COMPLEXITY LEVELS: PROMOTING HIGHER-ORDER THINKING
AND UNDERSTANDING THROUGH ENHANCED ASSESSMENT**

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the mathematics teachers' level of test construction practices and evaluated the teachers' level of application of cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity levels on test construction. The participants of this research are the public-school mathematics teachers from the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City from Key Stages 1 to 4, for the academic year 2022-2023. Based on the findings of the study, it was found that mathematics teachers have a high level of understanding and application of assessment principles. They also demonstrated a strong understanding of how to align test construction with the curriculum and learning objectives. The teachers also exhibited a high level of practice in the use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria to enhance the quality and fairness of assessments. Giving reflection and feedback is highly practiced by the teachers in assessment. The mathematics teachers also demonstrated a high level of application of cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity levels on test construction. On the other hand, the teachers' level of test construction practices such as knowledge of assessment principles, understanding of curriculum and learning objectives, utilization of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and giving reflection and feedback are all significantly related to their application of frameworks such as cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity levels in test construction. However, the differences among the teachers' level of test construction practices and application of frameworks when grouped according to profile are not all significant. The results of this study served as a basis for the action plan proposal to enhance assessment practices and improve learners' higher-order thinking skills.

Keywords: *assessment, knowledge dimension, learning complexity level, SOLO taxonomy*

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' knowledge, skills, and cognitive abilities. To facilitate effective teaching and learning, educators have explored various frameworks and models that provide a structured approach to curriculum development and assessment. Two widely recognized and influential frameworks in educational psychology are Bloom's Taxonomy and the Structure of Observed Learning Outcome (SOLO) framework. These frameworks offer valuable insights into the levels of cognitive complexity and learning progression. Test construction is a critical component of the educational assessment process, as it determines how effectively student learning is evaluated and measured. A well-constructed test not only assesses students' knowledge and understanding but also promotes higher-order thinking skills and deeper levels of cognitive engagement. One framework commonly used to guide test construction is Bloom's taxonomy, which provides a hierarchical structure for categorizing cognitive skills. In particular, Bloom's taxonomy's knowledge dimension plays a fundamental role in shaping the design and content of test items.

Bloom's Taxonomy, developed by Benjamin Bloom, is a hierarchical model that classifies learning objectives into different levels of cognitive complexity. The taxonomy consists of six levels: Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, Analysis, Synthesis, and Evaluation. Each level represents a distinct cognitive process that builds upon the previous one, allowing educators to design learning experiences that promote higher-order thinking skills. On the other hand, the knowledge dimension of Bloom's taxonomy focuses on the types and levels of knowledge that students can acquire. It categorizes knowledge into different levels, ranging from lower-order knowledge to higher-order knowledge. The taxonomy consists of four levels of knowledge: factual, conceptual, procedural, and metacognitive.

The SOLO framework, on the other hand, was developed by John B. Biggs and Kevin F. Collis as an alternative to Bloom's Taxonomy. It emphasizes the quality of understanding and learning outcomes rather than focusing solely on cognitive complexity. SOLO stands for the Structure of Observed Learning Outcome, and it categorizes students' understanding into five levels: Prestructural, Unistructural, Multistructural, Relational, and Extended Abstract. This framework provides a clear structure to assess students' understanding and guide their progress from simple and surface-level comprehension to deep and meaningful learning.

Both Bloom's Taxonomy and the SOLO framework have been widely adopted and applied in educational settings across various disciplines and levels of education. These frameworks serve as essential tools for educators to plan instruction, develop learning outcomes, and assess students' learning achievements. By incorporating these

frameworks into their teaching practices, educators can promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and higher-order cognitive skills among students. Despite their shared objective of promoting effective teaching and learning, Bloom's Taxonomy and the SOLO framework differ in their approaches and focus. While Bloom's Taxonomy provides a hierarchical structure for classifying learning objectives, the SOLO framework emphasizes the quality and depth of understanding. Recognizing the strengths and limitations of each framework is crucial for educators to select the most suitable approach for specific learning goals and contexts. This research aims to explore the relationship between Bloom's taxonomy and knowledge dimension levels, SOLO framework, and teachers' test construction practices.

According to Putri and Raharjo (2020), the purpose of developing these SOLO Taxonomy instruments is to measure and analyze the group of students' ability to learn and master a concept from various perspectives, aligning with the cognitive level of Piaget's theory. SOLO Taxonomy is a systematic framework that elucidates how learners progress from simplicity to complexity when acquiring different tasks or subjects. This taxonomy serves as a tool to enrich the quality of learning in classroom teaching, offering a methodical approach to cultivating profound understanding. It guides student learning in a manner that fosters depth (Damopoli, 2020).

Subyantoro (2014) underscored the compelling application of the Structure of Observed Learning Outcomes (SOLO) taxonomy as a method for assessing learning outcomes in educational settings, particularly within schools. It emphasizes the importance of students' capacity to establish meaningful connections among the various answers or solutions they propose. This distinctive approach aligns with contemporary educational paradigms, promoting a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of students' cognitive abilities and learning achievements.

Bueno et al. (2019) stated that teachers are the most important resource for developing student's identities. They influence the ways in which students' think of themselves in the classroom. In establishing equitable arrangements, effective teachers' pay attention to the different needs that result from different home environments, different languages, and different capabilities and perspectives. Ojales et al. (2021) observed that numerous schools and teachers are often viewed as resistant to the swift and substantial changes in the educational system. However, some educators readily accept, adapt to, and anticipate the positive transformations promised by these innovations. The Department of Education (DepEd), in particular, has been proactive in addressing the pertinent needs of Filipino learners. The department anticipates that teachers will adapt to the inevitable modifications in the system to ensure they remain on par with educational advancements in neighboring countries.

The results Gagani's (2017) study indicated a cognitive pattern in the ability to reason inductively in the context of geometry. The findings suggest that a lack of coherence and the inability to transfer knowledge to new tasks can hinder success. It was observed that participants who struggled with lower-level tasks were also less effective in higher-level tasks. Meanwhile, the research of Triana et al. (2023) found that SOLO

taxonomy levels can serve as a tool for evaluating critical thinking, applicable not only in posing questions, assignments, and assessment designs but also in reporting student learning outcomes. The study recommended utilization of SOLO taxonomy at the elementary school level as a tool for both assessing and reporting student learning outcomes.

This research explored and compared Bloom's Taxonomy and the SOLO framework, examining their theoretical foundations, practical applications, and effectiveness in promoting student learning. By investigating how different levels of knowledge are reflected in test items, the study sought to provide educators with practical guidelines for constructing assessments that effectively measure and promote student learning. Furthermore, it aims to contribute to the ongoing discourse on effective assessment practices and their alignment with learning objectives in educational settings.

Research Questions

This research sought results and findings to the following objectives.

1. Determine the profile of the mathematics teachers in terms of
 - 1.1. position,
 - 1.2. no. of years in service,
 - 1.3. educational attainment, and
 - 1.4. no. of assessment-related training.
2. Assess the teachers' level of test construction practices in terms of
 - 2.1. knowledge of assessment principles,
 - 2.2. understanding of curriculum and learning objectives,
 - 2.3. use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and
 - 2.4. giving reflection and feedback.
3. Evaluate the teachers' level of application of the following on test construction.
 - 3.1. cognitive process dimension
 - 3.2. knowledge dimension
 - 3.3. learning complexity levels
4. Find the difference among the teachers' level of test construction practices on knowledge of assessment principles, understanding of curriculum and learning objectives, use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and giving reflection and feedback when grouped according to profile.
5. Find the difference among the teachers' level of application of cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity on test construction when grouped according to profile.
6. Ascertain the relationship between teachers' level of test construction practices and level of application of cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity.
7. Propose a plan of action to enhance assessment practices and improve learners' higher-order thinking skills.

METHODOLOGY

This study is a descriptive correlational type of research. The study examined the relationship between two or more variables without making any claims about cause and effect. It includes collecting and analyzing data on at least two variables to see if there is a link between them. The participants of this research are the public-school mathematics teachers from the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City from Key Stages 1 to 4. Based on the data gathered by the Planning Officer from the Schools Governance and Operation Division, there are 597 teachers in the city schools division who teach mathematics. Using the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator, the recommended sample size obtained is 234 at 0.05 level of significance.

To elicit the information needed in this study, the researcher utilized a self-constructed validated questionnaire as the source of data. Part I is the respondents' profile which included their current position, educational attainment, length of service, and number of assessment-related training. Part II is the assessment of teachers' level of test construction practices in terms of knowledge of assessment principles, understanding of curriculum and learning objectives, use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and giving reflection and feedback. Part III is the evaluation of the teachers' level of application of cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and levels of learning complexity on test construction. The online survey questionnaire using Google Forms was distributed through the school mathematics coordinators within the Schools Division Office of San Pedro City.

Several statistical measures and tests were used to analyze the gathered data to answer the specified problems of the study. Weighted mean and composited mean were used to assess the teachers' level of test construction practices in terms of knowledge of assessment principles, understanding of curriculum and learning objectives, use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and giving reflection and feedback. Those were also used to evaluate the teachers' level of application of the cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity levels on test construction.

Pearson Correlation was utilized to statistically determine the significant relationship between the teachers' level of test construction practices and the level of application of cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity. Also, analysis of variance was used to determine the significant difference in teachers' level of test construction practices and level of application of cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity when grouped according to profile. The findings of the study were used to propose a plan of action to enhance assessment practices and improve learners' higher-order thinking skills.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part discusses the key findings and empirical results obtained in the study.

Table 1. Respondents' Profile in Terms of Position

Position	f	%
Teacher I	85	36.32
Teacher II	55	23.50
Teacher III	72	30.77
Head Teacher II	1	0.43
Head Teacher III	2	0.85
Master Teacher I	16	6.84
Master Teacher II	3	1.28
TOTAL	234	100.00

Table 1 presents the respondents' profile in terms of position. Majority of the respondents (85 or 36.32%) are Teacher I. Fifty-five (23.5%) are Teacher II and 72 (30.77%) are Teacher III. Three of the respondents are in Head Teacher position and 19 of them are already Master Teachers.

Table 2. Respondents' Profile in Terms of Length of Service

No. of Years in Service	f	%
0 - 5 years	37	15.81
6 - 10 years	69	29.29
11 - 15 years	56	23.93
16 - 20 years	28	11.97
21 - 25 years	18	7.69
26 or more years	26	11.11
TOTAL	234	100.00

Table 2 displays the respondents' profile in terms of length of service by the number of years. Majority of the respondents (69 or 29.29%) are six to ten years in service. Thirty-seven (15.81%) are at most five years in service and 56 (23.93%) of them are eleven to fifteen years in service already. Seventy-two of them are sixteen years or more in the service.

Table 3. Respondents' Profile in Terms of Number of Assessment-Related Training

No. of Training Attended	f	%
0 – 3	116	49.57
4 – 6	55	23.50
7 – 9	16	6.84
10 and above	47	20.09
TOTAL	234	100.00

Table 3 shows the respondents' profile in terms of number of assessment-related training. Majority of the respondents (116 or 49.57%) have 0 to 3 training related to assessment. Fifty-five (23.5%) have 4 to 6 trainings, 16 (6.84%) have 7 to 9 and 47 (20.09%) of them have 10 or more training related to assessment.

Table 4. Respondents' Profile in Terms of Highest Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	f	%
Bachelor's Degree	156	66.67
Master's Degree	76	32.48
Doctorate Degree	2	0.85
TOTAL	234	100.00

Table 4 presents the respondents' profile in terms of number of highest educational attainment. Majority of the respondents (156 or 66.67%) are Bachelor's Degree holder. Seventy-six (32.48%) are already graduated with Master's Degree and two (0.85%) are already with Doctorate Degree.

Table 5 on the next page displays the assessment of the level of test construction practices in terms of knowledge of assessment principles. The three indicators with the highest weighted mean indicate that the teachers utilize a range of assessment methods, including formative and summative assessments, to effectively track and monitor student progress. Also, the teachers place importance on fairness and equity in assessment, making conscious efforts to minimize bias in their evaluation processes. They also demonstrate an understanding of the significance of using valid and reliable assessment tools and techniques.

On the other hand, the three indicators with the lowest weighted mean imply that the teachers still have difficulties in designing assessments that align with the learning objectives and curriculum standards. Also, they face challenges in effectively analyzing assessment data to inform their instructional decisions and make necessary adjustments to their teaching strategies. The teachers also have limited engagement in seeking professional development opportunities to enhance their knowledge and understanding of assessment principles.

Table 5. Assessment of the Level of Test Construction Practices in Terms of Knowledge of Assessment Principles

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I use various assessment methods, such as formative and summative assessments, to monitor student progress.	3.74	High
I value the principles of fairness and equity in assessment and strive to minimize bias in their evaluation practices.	3.73	High
I understand the importance of using valid and reliable assessment tools and techniques.	3.72	High
I am aware of the benefits of involving students in the assessment process, such as self-assessment and peer assessment.	3.66	High
I am knowledgeable about the purposes and goals of assessment in the teaching and learning process.	3.65	High
I have a clear understanding of the different types of assessments available for evaluating student learning.	3.61	High
I use varied strategies for providing timely and constructive feedback to students based on assessment results.	3.55	High
I design assessments that align with the learning objectives and curriculum standards.	3.54	High
I analyze assessment data to inform their instructional decisions and adjust their teaching strategies accordingly.	3.53	High
I seek professional development opportunities to enhance their knowledge and understanding of assessment principles.	3.51	High
Composite Mean	3.62	High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 High 2.51 – 3.25 Moderate 1.76 – 2.50 Limited 1.00 – 1.75 Low

The composite mean of 3.62 implies that the teachers have a high level of practice of knowledge of assessment principles. It also signifies that the teachers have a high level of understanding and application of assessment principles.

Table 6 on the next page shows the assessment of the level of test construction practices in terms of understanding of the curriculum and learning objectives. The three indicators with the highest weighted mean indicate that the teachers focus on monitoring and addressing individual student needs. Also, the teachers demonstrate a purposeful and intentional approach to teaching. The teachers are also able to articulate the relevance and importance of the learning objectives to student learning and development, helping students understand the purpose and value of what they are learning.

Table 6. Assessment of the Level of Test Construction Practices in Terms of Understanding of Curriculum and Learning Objectives

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I assess student progress towards the learning objectives and adjust their teaching accordingly.	3.61	High
I incorporate the learning objectives into their lesson planning and instructional strategies.	3.60	High
I articulate the relevance and importance of learning objectives to student learning and development.	3.59	High
I collaborate with colleagues to ensure consistency in understanding and implementation of the curriculum and learning objectives.	3.59	High
I use various assessment methods to evaluate student mastery of the learning objectives.	3.57	High
I reflect on their teaching practices and adjust to better align with the curriculum and learning objectives.	3.56	High
I have a clear understanding of the overall curriculum framework and its alignment with educational standards.	3.56	High
I seek resources and materials that support the attainment of learning objectives.	3.54	High
I am familiar with the specific learning objectives outlined in the curriculum for each grade or subject area they teach.	3.53	High
I utilize differentiated instruction to meet the diverse needs and abilities of students in relation to the learning objectives.	3.47	High
Composite Mean	3.56	High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 High 2.51 – 3.25 Moderate 1.76 – 2.50 Limited 1.00 – 1.75 Low

Meanwhile, the indicators with the lowest weighted mean denote that there is a potential need for the teachers to actively explore and utilize relevant instructional resources to enhance student learning experiences. Also, the teachers exhibit less familiarity with the specific learning objectives outlined in the curriculum for each grade or subject area they teach. The teachers also demonstrate a lower utilization of differentiated

instruction to address the diverse needs and abilities of students in relation to the learning objectives.

The composite mean of 3.56 signifies that the teachers demonstrated a strong understanding of how to align test construction with the curriculum and learning objectives. They likely showed competence in developing assessments that accurately reflect the intended outcomes and content of the curriculum. Also, this indicates a positive performance in test construction practices related to understanding curriculum and learning objectives.

Table 7. Assessment of the Level of Test Construction Practices in Terms of Use of Effective Scoring Rubrics and Criteria

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I use scoring rubrics to ensure consistency and fairness in the evaluation of student work across different assessments and classrooms.	3.48	High
I provide specific and constructive feedback to students based on the criteria outlined in the scoring rubrics.	3.44	High
I use scoring rubrics as a tool for enhancing student learning and promoting meaningful feedback.	3.42	High
I use well-defined scoring rubrics to assess student work and provide clear expectations for performance.	3.42	High
I communicate the criteria and standards outlined in the scoring rubrics to students prior to assessments.	3.41	High
I review and revise scoring rubrics to ensure they align with the learning objectives and accurately assess student progress.	3.41	High
I use scoring rubrics to guide instructional decisions and identify areas where additional support or enrichment may be needed.	3.40	High
I provide opportunities for self-assessment and reflection using the scoring rubrics, allowing students to take ownership of their learning.	3.37	High
I receive training and support to effectively develop and use scoring rubrics and criteria in their assessment practices.	3.34	High
I involve students in the creation and use of scoring rubrics, promoting a shared understanding of expectations and assessment criteria.	3.32	High
Composite Mean	3.40	High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 High 2.51 – 3.25 Moderate 1.76 – 2.50 Limited 1.00 – 1.75 Low

Table 7 presents the assessment of the level of test construction practices in terms of use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria. The three indicators with the highest weighted mean indicate that the teachers show commitment to maintaining standards and

equitable evaluation practices. The teachers also focus on delivering targeted feedback that helps students understand their strengths and areas for improvement. Also, they demonstrate understanding of the value of rubrics in providing actionable feedback that supports students' growth and development. The teachers provide emphasis on the use of scoring rubrics to ensure consistency, provide constructive feedback, and promote student learning in their assessment practices.

On the other hand, the three indicators with the lowest weighted mean denote that teachers provide fewer opportunities for self-assessment and reflection using scoring rubrics, limiting students' ability to take ownership of their learning. Also, the teachers receive less training and support in effectively developing and using scoring rubrics and criteria in their assessment practices. There is a need for improvement in areas such as student self-assessment, teacher training, and involving students in the creation and use of scoring rubrics to enhance student engagement and understanding of assessment expectations.

The composite mean of 3.40 signifies a high level of practice in the use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria. The teachers develop and implement scoring rubrics and criteria to enhance the quality and fairness of assessments.

Table 8 on the next page shows the assessment of the level of test construction practices in terms of giving reflection and feedback. The three indicators with the highest weighted mean indicate that the teachers encourage students to analyze their own performance, fostering a reflective mindset where students identify their strengths and areas for growth. Also, the teachers provide constructive feedback to students that is specific, and helps them understand how to enhance their learning. The teachers also assist students in setting goals based on the feedback received and support them in developing strategies for improvement for the students to take responsibility for their learning progress and equip them with the necessary tools to make meaningful advancements.

On the other hand, the three indicators with the lowest weighted mean indicate potential opportunities for teachers to encourage more student engagement in providing feedback to their peers, fostering a collaborative learning environment. The teachers demonstrate a lower engagement in seeking professional development opportunities to enhance their ability to provide effective reflection and feedback. The findings also suggest the potential for teachers to explore a wider range of approaches to offer tailored and individualized feedback to meet the diverse needs of students.

The composite mean of 3.47 infers that giving reflection and feedback is highly practiced by the teachers in assessment. This finding also implies that the teachers demonstrate effective skills and strategies in providing reflection and feedback to students, aiding their learning and growth

Table 8. Assessment of the Level of Test Construction Practices in Terms of Giving Reflection and Feedback

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I encourage students to analyze their performance and identify areas of strength and areas for improvement.	3.53	High
I give constructive feedback to students that is specific, actionable, and helps them understand how to enhance their learning	3.53	High
I guide students in setting goals based on the feedback received and assist them in developing strategies for improvement.	3.50	High
I provide timely feedback on test assessments to ensure students can benefit from it in future learning activities.	3.48	High
I assist students understand the criteria used to evaluate their test performance and communicate clear expectations.	3.45	High
I provide students with opportunities for reflection and self-assessment after completing tests or assessments.	3.45	High
I engage in dialogue with students to clarify misunderstandings and address any questions or concerns related to their test results.	3.45	High
I involve students in the feedback process by promoting peer feedback and collaboration in analyzing test results.	3.44	High
I seek professional development opportunities to enhance their ability to provide effective reflection and feedback.	3.44	High
I use various methods, such as written comments, conferences, or digital tools, to provide personalized feedback to students.	3.39	High
Composite Mean	3.47	High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 High 2.51 – 3.25 Moderate 1.76 – 2.50 Limited 1.00 – 1.75 Low

. Table 9 on the next page presents the evaluation of the level of application of cognitive process dimension on test construction. The three indicators with the highest weighted mean infer that the teachers provide clear instructions and prompts in test questions, guiding students' cognitive engagement and facilitating their thinking processes. Also, the teachers review and revise test questions to ensure they accurately measure the targeted cognitive processes and reflect student understanding. Also, the teachers are aware of the cognitive processes involved in complex tasks and their ability to assess students' critical thinking, analysis, and synthesis skills.

Table 9. Evaluation of the Level of Application of Cognitive Process Dimension on Test Construction

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I align test questions with the intended cognitive processes specified in the learning objectives and curriculum standards.	3.53	High
I provide clear instructions and prompts in test questions to guide students' cognitive engagement and thinking processes.	3.45	High
I review and revise test questions to ensure they effectively measure the targeted cognitive processes and accurately reflect student understanding.	3.55	High
I understand the cognitive process dimension and its importance in assessing higher-order thinking skills.	3.49	High
I ensure that the difficulty level and cognitive demand of test questions are appropriate for the grade level and subject area being assessed.	3.51	High
I construct test questions that require students to apply their knowledge, think critically, solve problems, and demonstrate complex reasoning.	3.55	High
I use a variety of question formats, such as multiple-choice, short-answer, and essay questions, to assess different cognitive processes effectively.	3.54	High
I use a balanced mix of test items that assess both lower-level and higher-level cognitive processes.	3.50	High
I seek resources, professional development, and collaborate with colleagues to enhance their knowledge and application of the cognitive process dimension in test construction.	3.55	High
I incorporate various levels of cognitive processes in test construction.	3.47	High
Composite Mean	3.51	High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 High 2.51 – 3.25 Moderate 1.76 – 2.50 Limited 1.00 – 1.75 Low

Meanwhile, the three indicators with the lowest weighted mean indicate that there is a need for teachers to diversify their assessment strategies and include a wider range of question types and formats that target different cognitive skills. Also, the teachers demonstrate a lower level of seeking resources, professional development, and collaboration with colleagues to enhance their knowledge and application of the cognitive process dimension in test construction. The teachers also incorporate a variety of cognitive processes in their test construction practices to provide a comprehensive assessment of student learning and thinking abilities.

The composite mean of 3.51 signifies a high level of application of cognitive process dimension on test construction. The result also implies that the teachers demonstrate strong skills and understanding in incorporating various levels of cognitive processes into their test design.

Table 10. Evaluation of the Level of Application of Knowledge Dimension on Test Construction

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I align test questions with the intended knowledge levels specified in the learning objectives and curriculum standards.	3.57	High
I provide clear instructions and prompts in test questions to guide students' application and demonstration of their knowledge.	3.57	High
I construct test questions that require students to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts, analyze information, and evaluate different perspectives.	3.56	High
I understand the knowledge dimension and its importance in assessing students' knowledge and understanding of content.	3.56	High
I review and revise test questions to ensure they effectively measure the targeted knowledge dimensions and accurately reflect student understanding.	3.53	High
I ensure that the depth and breadth of knowledge assessed in test questions are appropriate for the grade level and subject area being evaluated.	3.52	High
I incorporate various levels of knowledge, such as factual, conceptual, procedural, and metacognitive, in test construction.	3.50	High
I use a balanced mix of test items that assess both foundational knowledge and higher-level conceptual understanding.	3.50	High
I use a variety of question formats, such as multiple-choice, fill-in-the-blanks, and problem-solving scenarios, to effectively assess different knowledge dimensions.	3.50	High
I seek resources, professional development, and collaborate with colleagues to enhance their knowledge and application of the knowledge dimension in test construction.	3.48	High
Composite Mean	3.53	High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 High 2.51 – 3.25 Moderate 1.76 – 2.50 Limited 1.00 – 1.75 Low

Table 10 displays the evaluation of the level of application of knowledge dimension on test construction. The three indicators with the highest weighted mean indicate that

the teachers prioritize alignment, clarity, and higher-order thinking skills in their test question construction. They help students understand what is expected of them and enable them to effectively showcase their understanding. The teachers exhibit a commitment to assessing higher-order thinking skills and promoting critical thinking and problem-solving abilities among students.

Meanwhile, the three indicators with the lowest weighted mean denote the need for teachers to diversify their assessment strategies and include a wider range of question types and formats that target different knowledge dimensions. There is also a need for the teachers to explore and incorporate a broader range of question formats that align with the intended learning outcomes and engage students in demonstrating their understanding; professional development, and collaboration with colleagues to enhance their knowledge and application of the knowledge dimension in test construction.

The composite mean of 3.53 signifies a high level of application of knowledge dimension on test construction. It reflects the individuals' ability to create assessments that accurately assess and evaluate students' knowledge across different dimensions and levels of understanding. The result also infers that the teachers demonstrate strong skills and understanding in aligning test items with different knowledge dimensions.

Table 11 on the next page shows the evaluation of the level of application of learning complexity levels on test construction. The three indicators with the highest weighted mean indicate that the teachers are aware of the different cognitive demands associated with varying levels of complexity and can design assessments that align with these levels, they ensure that students understand the expectations and are able to demonstrate their knowledge and skills effectively, and they select assessment methods that suit the specific cognitive demands of different learning objectives and complexity levels.

On the other hand, the three indicators with the lowest weighted mean imply that the teachers still need continuous learning and collaborative efforts in staying updated with effective practices and strategies for assessing learning complexity, they also need to ensure that their assessments align with the expected cognitive demands outlined in the educational objectives and standards, and they need to design assessments that encompass a range of complexity levels, including both foundational knowledge and higher-order thinking skills.

Table 11. Evaluation of the Level of Application of Learning Complexity Levels on Test Construction

	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
I understand the learning complexity levels and their importance in assessing students' progress and growth.	3.46	High
I provide clear instructions and prompts in test questions to guide students' thinking and problem-solving processes at different complexity levels.	3.45	High
I use variety of question formats, such as multiple-choice, open-ended, and performance-based tasks, to effectively assess different learning complexity levels.	3.45	High
I review and revise test questions to ensure they effectively measure the targeted learning complexity levels and accurately reflect student abilities.	3.45	High
I construct test questions that require students to demonstrate their understanding, apply their knowledge, analyze information, and synthesize ideas.	3.44	High
I ensure that the difficulty and complexity of test questions are appropriate for the grade level and subject area being assessed.	3.44	High
I use a balanced mix of test items that assess both foundational knowledge and higher-order thinking skills.	3.42	High
I seek resources, professional development, and collaborate with colleagues to enhance their knowledge and application of learning complexity levels in test construction.	3.42	High
I align test questions with the intended learning complexity levels specified in the learning objectives and curriculum standards.	3.40	High
I incorporate various levels of learning complexity, such as pre-structural, unistructural, multiscriptual, relational, and extended abstract in test construction.	3.32	High
Composite Mean	3.43	High

Legend: 3.26 – 4.00 High 2.51 – 3.25 Moderate 1.76 – 2.50 Limited 1.00 – 1.75 Low

The composite mean of 3.43 signifies a high level of application of learning complexity levels on test construction on test construction. This indicates that the teachers assessed demonstrate strong skills and understanding in aligning test items with the appropriate levels of learning complexity. They have a solid grasp of how to design assessments that effectively measure and assess different levels of learning complexity as outlined in the learning objectives and curriculum standards.

Table 12. The Difference Among the Teachers' Level of Test Construction Practices When Grouped According to Position

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Knowledge of Assessment Principles	Between Groups	1.529	6	.255	1.893	.083
	Within Groups	30.552	227	.135		
	Total	32.081	233			
Understanding of Curriculum and Learning Objectives	Between Groups	1.403	6	.234	1.583	.153
	Within Groups	33.528	227	.148		
	Total	34.931	233			
Use of Effective Scoring Rubrics and Criteria	Between Groups	2.055	6	.343	1.688	.125
	Within Groups	46.074	227	.203		
	Total	48.130	233			
Giving Reflection and Feedback	Between Groups	1.823	6	.304	1.296	.260
	Within Groups	53.220	227	.234		
	Total	55.043	233			

The difference is significant when the p-value < 0.05.

Table 12 presents the difference among the teachers' level of test construction practices when grouped according to the current position. When grouped according to current teaching position, the difference in the teachers' level of test construction practices such as knowledge of assessment principles ($p = .083$), understanding of curriculum and learning objectives ($p = .153$), use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria ($p = .125$), and giving reflection and feedback ($p = .260$) is not significant. These results suggest that regardless of their specific roles or positions within the teaching profession, teachers demonstrate a similar level of proficiency and competence in these areas of test construction practices. The findings imply that the essential aspects of test construction practices are consistently applied across different teaching positions, indicating a uniform understanding and implementation of these practices among teachers.

Table 13 on the next page presents the difference among the teachers' level of test construction practices when grouped according to the length of service. When grouped according to the number of years in service, the difference in the teachers' level of test construction practices such as knowledge of assessment principles ($p = .001$), understanding of curriculum and learning objectives ($p = .001$), and giving reflection and feedback ($p = .260$) is significant. These results suggest that teachers with different years of experience demonstrate varying levels of proficiency and competence in these areas

of test construction practices. However, the difference in the use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria ($p = .086$) as a practice on test construction is not significant.

Table 13. The Difference Among the Teachers' Level of Test Construction Practices When Grouped According to Length of Service

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Knowledge of Assessment Principles	Between Groups	2.744	5	.549	4.266	.001
	Within Groups	29.336	228	.129		
	Total	32.081	233			
Understanding of Curriculum and Learning Objectives	Between Groups	3.114	5	.623	4.463	.001
	Within Groups	31.818	228	.140		
	Total	34.931	233			
Use of Effective Scoring Rubrics and Criteria	Between Groups	1.981	5	.396	1.958	.086
	Within Groups	46.148	228	.202		
	Total	48.130	233			
Giving Reflection and Feedback	Between Groups	3.129	5	.626	2.748	.020
	Within Groups	51.915	228	.228		
	Total	55.043	233			

The difference is significant when the p-value < 0.05 .

These findings imply that the application of scoring rubrics and criteria remains consistent regardless of the years of experience, indicating a shared understanding and implementation of this practice among teachers across different levels of tenure. These results are relevant to the study of Alkharusi (2016) which found significant differences in levels of adherence to the ethical principles in educational assessment among teachers with respect to teaching experience.

Table 14 on the next page displays the difference among the teachers' level of test construction practices when grouped according to the number of assessment-related training. The difference in the application of knowledge assessment principles ($p = .005$) as a practice on test construction is significant. This indicates that teachers who have undergone different levels of assessment training demonstrate varying levels of proficiency in applying knowledge assessment principles in their test construction practices.

Table 14. The Difference Among the Teachers' Level of Test Construction Practices When Grouped According to the Number of Assessment-Related Training

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Knowledge of Assessment Principles	Between Groups	1.749	3	.583	4.421	.005
	Within Groups	30.332	230	.132		
	Total	32.081	233			
Understanding of Curriculum and Learning Objectives	Between Groups	.962	3	.321	2.171	.092
	Within Groups	33.970	230	.148		
	Total	34.931	233			
Use of Effective Scoring Rubrics and Criteria	Between Groups	1.197	3	.399	1.955	.122
	Within Groups	46.933	230	.204		
	Total	48.130	233			
Giving Reflection and Feedback	Between Groups	1.146	3	.382	1.630	.183
	Within Groups	53.897	230	.234		
	Total	55.043	233			

The difference is significant when the p-value < 0.05.

However, the difference in the teachers' level of test construction practices such as understanding of curriculum and learning objectives ($p = .092$), use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria ($p = .168$), and giving reflection and feedback ($p = .137$) is not significant. This suggests that these aspects of test construction practices are consistently applied regardless of the level of assessment training, indicating a shared understanding and implementation among teachers in these areas. These results are relevant to the study of Alkharusi (2016) which found significant differences in levels of adherence to the ethical principles in educational assessment among teachers with respect to training in educational assessment.

Table 15 on the next page shows the difference among the teachers' level of test construction practices when grouped according to highest educational attainment. When the respondents are grouped according to their highest educational attainment, the difference in the teachers' level of test construction practices such as knowledge of assessment principles ($p = .247$), understanding of curriculum and learning objectives ($p = .364$), use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria ($p = .168$), and giving reflection and feedback ($p = .137$) is not significant.

Table 15. The Difference Among the Teachers' Level of Test Construction Practices When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Knowledge of Assessment Principles	Between Groups	.386	2	.193	1.406	.247
	Within Groups	31.695	231	.137		
	Total	32.081	233			
Understanding of Curriculum and Learning Objectives	Between Groups	.304	2	.152	1.015	.364
	Within Groups	34.627	231	.150		
	Total	34.931	233			
Use of Effective Scoring Rubrics and Criteria	Between Groups	.739	2	.369	1.801	.168
	Within Groups	47.391	231	.205		
	Total	48.130	233			
Giving Reflection and Feedback	Between Groups	.940	2	.470	2.006	.137
	Within Groups	54.104	231	.234		
	Total	55.043	233			

The difference is significant when the p-value < 0.05.

These findings imply that the essential components of test construction practices are consistently applied across different educational attainment levels, indicating a shared understanding and implementation of these practices among teachers irrespective of their highest level of education. These results are relevant to the study of Alkharusi (2016) which found significant differences in levels of adherence to the ethical principles in educational assessment among teachers with respect to educational qualification.

Table 16. The Difference Among the Teachers' Level of Application of the Frameworks on Test Construction When Grouped According to Position

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Cognitive Process Dimension	Between Groups	2.415	6	.403	2.315	.034
	Within Groups	39.468	227	.174		
	Total	41.883	233			
Knowledge Dimension	Between Groups	2.895	6	.482	2.775	.013
	Within Groups	39.459	227	.174		
	Total	42.354	233			
Learning Complexity Levels	Between Groups	2.757	6	.459	2.037	.062
	Within Groups	51.209	227	.226		
	Total	53.966	233			

The difference is significant when the p-value < 0.05.

Table 16 from the last page displays the difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks on test construction when grouped according to position. When grouped according to the current position, the difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks such as cognitive process dimension ($p = .034$) and knowledge dimension ($p = .013$) are significant. These findings suggest that teachers in

different positions within the teaching profession demonstrate varying levels of proficiency and competence in applying these frameworks in their test construction practices. However, the difference in the teachers' level of application of learning complexity levels ($p = .062$) on test construction is not significant. This implies that the incorporation of learning complexity levels remains consistent across different teaching positions, indicating a shared understanding and implementation of this practice among teachers regardless of their specific roles or positions within the profession.

Table 17. The Difference Among the Teachers' Level of Application of the Frameworks on Test Construction When Grouped According to Length of Service

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Cognitive Process Dimension	Between Groups	2.237	5	.447	2.573	.027
	Within Groups	39.646	228	.174		
	Total	41.883	233			
Knowledge Dimension	Between Groups	3.490	5	.698	4.095	.001
	Within Groups	38.864	228	.170		
	Total	42.354	233			
Learning Complexity Levels	Between Groups	2.450	5	.490	2.169	.058
	Within Groups	51.516	228	.226		
	Total	53.966	233			

The difference is significant when the p-value < 0.05.

Table 17 presents the difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks on test construction when grouped according to length of service. When grouped according to the number of years in service, the difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks such as cognitive process dimension ($p = .027$) and knowledge dimension ($p = .001$) are significant. These findings suggest that teachers with different years of experience demonstrate varying levels of proficiency and competence in applying these frameworks in their test construction practices. However, the difference in the teachers' level of application of learning complexity levels ($p = .058$) on test construction is not significant. This implies that the incorporation of learning complexity levels remains consistent across different levels of tenure, indicating a shared understanding and implementation of this practice among teachers regardless of their length of service.

Table 18. The Difference Among the Teachers' Level of Application of the Frameworks on Test Construction When Grouped According to the Number of Assessment-Related Training

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Cognitive Process Dimension	Between Groups	2.293	3	.764	4.441	.005
	Within Groups	39.590	230	.172		
	Total	41.883	233			

Knowledge Dimension	Between Groups	.769	3	.256	1.417	.239
	Within Groups	41.585	230	.181		
	Total	42.354	233			
Learning Complexity Levels	Between Groups	1.495	3	.498	2.185	.091
	Within Groups	52.471	230	.228		
	Total	53.966	233			

The difference is significant when the p-value < 0.05.

Table 18 displays the difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks on test construction when grouped according to the number of assessment-related training. When grouped according to the number of assessment-related training, the difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks such as cognitive process dimension ($p = .005$) is significant. This indicates that teachers with different levels of assessment training demonstrate varying levels of proficiency and competence in applying the cognitive process dimension in their test construction practices. However, the difference in the teachers' level of application knowledge dimension ($p = .239$) and learning complexity levels ($p = .091$) on test construction is not significant. These results suggest that the incorporation of the knowledge dimension and learning complexity levels remains consistent regardless of the level of assessment training, indicating a shared understanding and implementation of these practices among teachers across different levels of training.

Table 19 on the next page shows the difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks on test construction when grouped according to highest educational attainment. When the teachers are grouped according to their highest educational attainment, the difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks such as cognitive process dimension ($p = .074$), knowledge dimension ($p = .051$), and learning complexity levels ($p = .181$) on test construction is not significant.

Table 19. The Difference Among the Teachers' Level of Application of the Frameworks on Test Construction When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Cognitive Process Dimension	Between Groups	.936	2	.468	2.640	.074
	Within Groups	40.948	231	.177		
	Total	41.883	233			
Knowledge Dimension	Between Groups	1.080	2	.540	3.023	.051
	Within Groups	41.273	231	.179		
	Total	42.354	233			
Learning	Between Groups	.793	2	.396	1.722	.181

Complexity Levels	Within Groups	53.173	231	.230
	Total	53.966	233	

The difference is significant when the p-value < 0.05.

These findings suggest that regardless of their educational backgrounds, teachers demonstrate a similar level of proficiency and competence in applying these frameworks in their test construction practices. The findings imply that the essential components of these frameworks are consistently applied across different levels of educational attainment, indicating a shared understanding and implementation of these practices among teachers irrespective of their highest level of education.

Table 20. Correlation Between the Teachers' Application of Frameworks and Test Construction Practices

		Knowledge of Assessment Principles	Understanding of Curriculum and Learning Objectives	Use of Effective Scoring Rubrics and Criteria	Giving Reflection and Feedback
Cognitive Process Dimension	Pearson Correlation	.683**	.715**	.631**	.701**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	234	234	234	234
Knowledge Dimension	Pearson Correlation	.733**	.731**	.668**	.726**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	234	234	234	234
Learning Complexity Levels	Pearson Correlation	.615**	.677**	.673**	.704**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	234	234	234	234

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 20 presents the correlation between the teachers' application of frameworks and test construction practices. At 0.01 level of significance, the teachers' application of cognitive process dimension framework is significantly related to their construction practices such as demonstrating level of knowledge of assessment principles ($r = .683$), understanding of curriculum and learning objectives ($r = .715$), use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria ($r = .631$), and giving reflection and feedback ($r = .701$). This suggests that teachers who effectively apply the cognitive process dimension framework are more likely to exhibit a higher level of competence in these test construction practices. The results also imply the importance of incorporating the cognitive process dimension framework into teacher training and development programs to enhance teachers' ability to design and implement assessments that align with desired learning outcomes and promote meaningful feedback and reflection for students. These results are related to the findings of Dagostino (2014) that classification by cognitive level allows teachers to measure specific cognitive abilities assessed during tests. The study of Kaymak (2022)

also showed how Bloom's taxonomy can be utilized to develop a clear methodology for creating a test for solving skills and experimental assessment of students' performance.

Also, the teachers' application of knowledge dimension framework is significantly related to their construction practices such as demonstrating level of knowledge of assessment principles ($r = .733$), understanding of curriculum and learning objectives ($r = .731$), use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria ($r = .668$), and giving reflection and feedback ($r = .726$), at 0.01 level of significance. This implies that teachers who effectively apply the knowledge dimension framework are more likely to exhibit a higher level of proficiency in these test construction practices. The results also denote the importance of integrating the knowledge dimension framework into teacher training and development programs, as it can enhance teachers' ability to create assessments that align with the intended knowledge outcomes and facilitate meaningful feedback and reflection for students. These results are relevant to the study of Long (2014) which found that each dimension is applicable to mathematics because the levels provide the necessary coherence required when assessing mathematical tasks that may demand not only basic recall but also the highest level of creativity. Meanwhile, it is in contrast with the results of Banda (2023) which found that the majority of the lecturers did not illustrate how to use Bloom's Taxonomy in planning a course of study, setting objectives or outcomes, creating learning activities or creating assessment tasks for students. There is no relationship between lecturers' use of learning outcomes as a basis for preparing class tasks and their assertions that they compared objectives with tasks prepared for students.

Lastly, at 0.01 level of significance, the teachers' application of learning complexity levels is significantly related to their construction practices such as demonstrating level of knowledge of assessment principles ($r = .615$), understanding of curriculum and learning objectives ($r = .677$), use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria ($r = .673$), and giving reflection and feedback ($r = .704$). This indicates that teachers who effectively apply the concept of learning complexity levels in their test construction practices are more likely to demonstrate a higher level of proficiency in the mentioned areas. The findings underscore the importance of considering learning complexity levels as a framework in teacher training and development programs to enhance teachers' ability to design assessments that align with the varying cognitive demands of learning tasks. These results are related to the study of Panizzon (2017)

These results suggest that teachers who demonstrate a higher level of proficiency and competence in these test construction practices are more likely to effectively apply the frameworks in their assessment processes. The findings also imply the interconnectedness between the foundational test construction practices and the application of frameworks, indicating that a comprehensive and well-rounded approach to test construction requires a strong foundation in assessment principles and effective practices.

Table 21. Program Proposal for Enhancement of Assessment Practices and Improvement of Learners' Higher-Order Thinking Skills in Mathematics

Specific Objectives	Activities	Implementing Bodies	Time Frame	Results	Budget
1. To capacitate trainers in understanding and cascading the HOTS Professional Learning Packages.	Regional Training of Trainers on the Higher-Order Thinking Skills Professional Learning Packages	CLMD Chief Education Program Supervisors Core Team of Trainers NEAP	SY 2023-2024	Capacitated Trainers for the Cascading of HOTS PLPs	SEF MOOE HRD Fund
2. To offer teachers the chance to learn, utilize, and share the SOLO Model to enhance and promote higher-order thinking skills.	Division Training of Teachers on the Higher-Order Thinking Skills Professional Learning Packages	CID Chief Education Program Supervisors PSDS School Head Teachers	SY 2023-2024	Trained Teachers in Utilizing the SOLO Model to Classroom Assessment	SEF MOOE HRD Fund
3. To develop quality assured SOLO-type test items and activity sheets for enhanced assessment practices	School LAC and INSET on developing SOLO-type test items and activity sheets	PSDS School Head Trained Teachers Teachers	SY 2023-2024	Improved DAT or NAT Results Improved Results in Basic Education Exit Assessment Test Improved MPS	SEF MOOE HRD Fund

Conclusions

The teachers exhibit high level of test construction practices on demonstrating knowledge of assessment principles, understanding of the curriculum and learning objectives, use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and giving reflection and feedback. Also, the teachers demonstrate high level of application of cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity levels in test construction.

When grouped according to the current teaching position, the difference in the teachers' level of test construction practices such as knowledge of assessment principles, understanding of curriculum and learning objectives, use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and giving reflection and feedback is not significant.

The difference in the teachers' level of test construction practices such as knowledge of assessment principles, understanding of curriculum and learning objectives, and giving reflection and feedback is significant when the respondents are grouped according to the length of service. However, the difference in the use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria as a practice on test construction is not significant.

When the respondents are grouped according to their highest educational attainment, the difference in the teachers' level of test construction practices such as knowledge of assessment principles, understanding of curriculum and learning objectives, use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and giving reflection and feedback is not significant.

When grouped according to the current teaching position, the difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks such as cognitive process dimension and knowledge dimension are significant. However, the difference in the teachers' level of application of learning complexity levels on test construction is not significant.

When grouped according to the number of assessment-related training, the difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks such as cognitive process dimension is significant. However, the difference in the teachers' level of application knowledge dimension and learning complexity levels on test construction is not significant.

The difference in the application of knowledge assessment principles as a practice on test construction is significant when the respondents are grouped according to the number of assessment-related training. However, the difference in the teachers' level of test construction practices such as understanding of curriculum and learning objectives, use of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and giving reflection and feedback is not significant.

The difference among the teachers' level of application of the frameworks such as cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity levels on

test construction is not significant when the teachers are grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

The teachers' level of test construction practices such as demonstrating knowledge of assessment principles, understanding of curriculum and learning objectives, utilization of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and giving reflection and feedback are all significantly related to their application of frameworks such as cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity levels in test construction.

Recommendations

It is suggested that teacher training and professional development programs in the educational sector may include enhancing teachers' knowledge and application of assessment principles, understanding of curriculum and learning objectives, utilization of effective scoring rubrics and criteria, and giving reflection and feedback. School administrators may consider organizing workshops, seminars, or ongoing training sessions to support teachers in improving their test construction practices. These sessions may provide guidance on aligning test questions with learning objectives, utilizing various question formats, and incorporating different levels of learning complexity.

It is recommended that school principals encourage a collaborative environment where teachers can share best practices related to test construction and assessment. This can be facilitated through regular team meetings, peer observations, or professional learning communities. School principals may consider establishing a system for continuous evaluation and feedback on test construction practices, allowing teachers to receive constructive input and guidance for improvement. This could foster a culture of ongoing professional growth and refinement of assessment practices within the school.

The findings of the study also suggest teachers to actively seek resources, attend professional development opportunities, and engage in collaborative discussions with colleagues to further enhance their understanding and application of frameworks such as the cognitive process dimension, knowledge dimension, and learning complexity levels in test construction. Teachers are recommended to regularly review and update their assessment practices based on emerging research and best practices in the field. Staying informed about current trends and advancements in assessment can contribute to the continuous improvement of their test construction practices.

School administrators and teachers may consider involving students in the assessment process by providing opportunities for self-assessment, peer feedback, and reflection. This can empower students to take ownership of their learning and provide valuable insights into their progress. It is suggested that schools provide access to a range of assessment resources, including sample test questions, scoring rubrics, and

exemplars, to support teachers in developing high-quality assessments that align with learning objectives and promote student growth.

Lastly, future researchers may explore other aspects related to test construction practices, such as the impact of cultural factors, technology integration, and innovative assessment methods. Investigating these facets could contribute to a comprehensive understanding of effective assessment practices and further enhance the field of educational assessment. Also, it is suggested that future research explore the impact of ongoing support and mentoring for teachers in improving their test construction practices. Investigating the effectiveness of long-term interventions and their sustained impact on assessment practices can provide valuable insights for teacher training and development programs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research instrument was submitted to the Chief Education Program Supervisor and Senior Education Program Specialist for Planning and Research for purpose, content, and structure validation. A dry run was conducted to obtain data for the reliability test. After the finalization of the research instrument, a letter was submitted to the Schools Division Superintendent to seek approval for the dissemination of the survey questionnaire. An endorsement from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent was released to the researcher allowing the distribution of the online survey questionnaire to the respondents.

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